

Digital Transformation of Management Education

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ABSTRACT:- Digital transformation in education can enhance instructional learning, especially in higher education by creating a blended learning experience that combines both traditional classroom-based methods and modern technology. In this research paper we will analyse how the digital transformation of the management education will impact in the education system, how would it be helpful for all the others and how we can utilise the digital studies that it can be beneficial for the upcoming generation.

Keywords:- Digital Transformation, 21st-century necessity, Educational Management, Technology, Digital Strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation (DT) is essential for all fields, regardless of their size and sector of activity. Beyond the dematerialization of work processes, this approach allows management system to optimize their operations, and to gain in performance, efficiency, and competitiveness through the adoption of a new management mode, new tools, new methods of work but also new reflections and organizations. The DT has become a significant topic of concern and a strategic issue for all management system. It offers new opportunities for students, beyond their traditional activities, by accelerating their growth and creating sustainable competitive advantages and security of operations. The DT increases the profitability of the education system by simplifying processes and interactions within the management and students.

Digital transformation means transforming an organization's core business to better meet customer needs by leveraging technology and data. In education, that target customer is often students, though it could also be faculty, staff, alumni, and others. As the educational sector becomes more competitive, digital transformation is now becoming a necessary means of survival as this new digital world requires educators to adapt and adopt digital technologies, methodologies and mindsets. To understand how a full and sustainable digital transformation can take place, it's important to examine the potential challenges or roadblocks an institution might face. The goal of this paper is to give an overview of the literature regarding digital transformation into management education and to analyze how it is used in practice in regard to: time component; country of case origin; case industry and; digital transformation focus.

Digital transformation in education is a 21st -century necessity. Right from schooling to higher education, every level of our learning system is affected by technology. Rapidly evolving technology is transforming the way knowledge is imparted and absorbed today. Increasing digitalization making way for new communication instruments enabling faster knowledge sharing in schools and colleges. It is redefining learning models in education and skill development.

A digital transformation process consists of information technology implementation projects, as well as organizational factors such as top management support, digital transformation strategy, and organizational changes. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is little evidence about digital transformation endeavors in organizations and how they perceive it – is it only about digital technologies adoption or a true organizational shift is needed? In order to address this issue and as the first step in our research project, a literature review is conducted. The analysis included case study papers from Scopus and Web of Science databases.

Four goals of digital transformation: -

1. Enhanced competitiveness,
2. Higher profitability,
3. Better customer experience, and
4. Greater agility across the enterprise.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital transformation strategy is a blueprint that supports companies in governing the transformations that arise owing to the integration of digital technologies, as well as in their operations after a transformation. Matt et al.(2015)Digital transformation is concerned with the changes digital technologies can bring about in a company's business model, which result in changed products or organizational structures or the automation of processes. These changes can be observed in the rising demand for Internet-based media, which has led to changes in entire business models (for example, in the music industry). Hess et al. (2016) The use of new digital technologies (social media, mobile, analytics, or embedded devices) to enable significant business improvements (such as enhancing customer experience, streamlining operations, or creating new business models). Liere-Netheler et al. (2018) Digital transformation as encompassing the digitization of sales and communication channels and the digitization of a firm's offerings (products and services), which replace or augment physical offerings. Furthermore, digital transformation entails tactical and strategic business moves that are triggered by datadriven insights and the launch of digital business models that allow new ways of capturing value. Horlach et al. (2017) The use of technology to radically improve performance or reach of enterprises. Westermann et al. (2011)

III. OBJECTIVES

1. What is the current status of digital intervention in India?
2. What are the opportunities for adopting digital technologies in India?
3. What is the roadmap for change?
4. Emerging trends of digital education
5. Model of facilitating factors for Digital learning.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

4.1 What is the current status of digital intervention in India.

Today, producing knowledge has a great importance as well as acquiring knowledge. It seems that the success of the individual, the institution or the society depends on the activity of producing and using information. The increase in the use and production of knowledge places societies into a necessary transformation. One of the most important events in history is the industrial (industrial) revolution which has the potential to transform society.

Developments and innovations in technology over the past 20 years give us the opportunity to access time and space without any hassle. Considering the possibilities offered by technology for social and economic development, it is considered appropriate for the stratum of globalization to come into the technological dimension to be called "digital age", "Information age", "information society"

Speed: New technologies that are connected to each other and are very versatile move quickly at an exponential speed, triggering each other.

Width and Depth: Digitization speeds up the industry 4.0. However, the increase in technology diversity in the industry has brought about the change.

System Impact: Industry 4.0 is expected to undergo a total change as digital industries, companies, and even countries.

Technological trends - increasing internet use and the development of internet technologies.

The shift to digital learning is troublesome because no one was ready until the COVID-19 took hold. The real factors of the 21st century have changed the way we deliver/access information, share knowledge, and ease learning. The COVID-19 pandemic and its resultant impact on our lives have raised the need to adopt innovative ways of getting education services at all levels.

In recent time due to novel CORONA-19 pandemic education system started realizing the importance and implementing the digitalization into their system by adapting it. Today all the classes are running on online platform such as zoom, google meet etc. Which made digital platform to play an important role into the education system.

In past years where practical subjects seems to be difficult to study online where in today's conditions every aspect to gain knowledge in any field made it possible by bring digitalizing in education system. The advanced technologies have the ability to plan, manage, and support digital transformation needs for the education industry. It can help institutions move their focus away from traditional learning models to adopt digital. This motivates immersive learning experiences, future-ready staff, and strategic outcomes.

4.2 What are the opportunities for adopting digital technologies in India.

Today, many business schools are beginning to develop digitization strategies for expanding outreach as well as delivering more customized programs. However, this should constitute only the first phase of the digitization process. Ultimately, the institution needs to embrace the enterprise resource planning (ERP) paradigm, which has found considerable success throughout the business community of practice. The digitization of management education need not be limited to simply webinars and podcasts but should encompass a much wider range of programs and services, such as, student recruiting.

Ironically, cases of business successes and failures in responding to digital transformation are a key theme in many management education strategy courses.

4.3 What is the roadmap for change.

These foundational elements are based on the work that Sprint and Insight Consultancy Solutions have done with schools. The elements work together to create the foundations for the successful implementation of a digital learning program and for any other strategy and change program:

- Leadership: the ability to have a vision, share that vision and inspire others to support your vision
- Vision and Goals: articulating what your school/district would be like with digital learning and the overarching goal(s) to get there
- Governance: the creation of structure and processes to manage work to deliver the goals
- Buy-in: determining how to engage stakeholders and get support behind required actions
- Culture: the values, behaviors and ways in which things are done
- Design and Planning: determining how best to test, organize and implement your program
- Budgeting and Funding: the financial resources needed and the sources of these
- Communication and Community: sharing and explaining what we are doing and why to staff, students, parents and community organizations
- Measurement and Evaluation: assessing impact, learning from this and using these learnings to improve the program

The 7 core elements in the centre of the digital learning roadmap are interrelated components for digital learning. These are:

- Home Connectivity
- Computing Devices
- Internet Safety
- Internet Infrastructure
- Tech Support
- Professional Development
- Digital Curriculum

4.4 Emerging trends of digital education

Digitalized classroom/Flipped Class rooms a growing Trend

A complete revolution in the way we learn today has been brought by Technology. Teachers teaching in the Classroom can capture the students and the full strength in the class by digital screens, thus facilitating each Child to get the same base content and input from the teachers. This feature of digital era has increased the Student engagement as it combines various instructional styles.

Video based learning.

Video-based learning as a part of digital marketing has geared up in Indian Education Sector and has made Education engaging, entertaining and exploring. It enables learning with a pedigree of learning out of leisure With creativity, fun and entertainment on cards via the wonderful Apps, podcasts, videos, interactive software, e Books and online interactive electronic boards. Children are excited and operative with interest to manage the Showcase via their intelligence, exploring the weak techno skills of teachers and assist them in public with pride And honour and recognition.

Massive open online course (MOOCS) & Other distant learning programs

A massive open online course (MOOC) is an online course aimed at unlimited participation and open access via The web. India is considered to be the biggest market for moocs in the world after the USA. Since the Population of India is huge, massive open online course (MOOC) are said to gateways for a lot of Indians in Terms of bringing an educational revolution. Online distant learning programs give a great opportunity to avail High quality learning with the help of internet connectivity.

K12 sector Game based learning

K-12 School is a terminology used as Kindergarten through XII grade. Various start-up companies have been The contributor for this sector. Today the world is of Y-generation people who are acquainted with the Technological developments taking around them, and they are also surrounded with the required skills and Abilities. K-12 creates the game-based learning environment, which enables the learner to easily get the word of education in India and give us a better self-trained Y generation.

3.5 Model of facilitating factors for Digital learning.

V. CHALLENGES

1. Resistance to change
2. Learners Motivation
3. Technological Skills of Learners
4. Evaluating effectiveness
5. Adaptability

VI. OPPORTUNITIES

1. No Physical Boundaries
2. More Engagement
3. Cost Effective
4. High engagement learning
5. Quality learning products.

VII. CONCLUSION

With so many different ways to define e-learning and the educational approaches that can be taken in these learning environments, it is the conclusion of this author that e-learning is an innovative approach to learning. It is a holistic way of teaching and learning that meets the needs of today’s digital natives. It is an

environment made up of collaboration, choice, and an array of technological resources that supports a successful online learning experience. However, in order for learners to be successful in this learning environment the challenges to e-learning must be overcome with support and a best practice solution. Instructors and learners must embrace the shift away from traditional classroom practices to an e-learning approach to education. Despite the fact that today's learners are digital natives, the use of technology for e-learning can be overwhelming and provide student motivation challenges however, with the proper supports from instructors, learners can be successful within these e-learning environments. Finally, and probably the most important challenge for the instructor is to focus on the overall elements of a well-developed course. Developing a purposeful and well-defined online course, which supports the instructor and learner, means devoting the appropriate time and embedding the applicable course elements into the e-learning environment

VIII. LIMITATIONS

1. It may be a solo act.
2. It may be impersonal.
3. Too much time spent in front of a computer screen may be harmful.
4. It requires self-discipline.
5. Possible lack of control

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